

HPC Plan for Stream 1 core integrations MS22 v1.0

The data provided by the individual groups (see tickets linked to from [WP9/Milestone22](#)) has been aggregated into a spreadsheet model of the data flow within PRIMAVERA.

There are several caveats to the spreadsheet model; it is assumed that all data is going to be immediately transferred to JASMIN. In the case of the Met Office simulations all data will be transferred to the Met Office archives first, so simulations will not be constrained by data transfer methods. Other groups may have similar arrangements.

Headlines

Total HPC usage and Data generated

HPC	Groups involved	Total HPC time (M Core hours)	Data volume generated (TB)
BSC:Marenostrom	BSC	8.9	218
CMCC:IBM iDataPlex	CMCC	17.3	460
DKRZ:ATOS/BULL X	MPG & AWI	25.0	283
KNMI:BULLX B500	KNMI	10.3	293
Met Office:Cray XC40	METOFFICE	56.8	453
Meteo France:Bullx	CERFACS	3.4	163
Munich:Supermuc	CNR	7.9	293
SMHI:Beskow (Cray)	SMHI	6.5	293
		Total:	2,456

Source: ["Summary data pivot" worksheet](#)

The data volume reported here is the estimated data volume based on early estimates of output needed for HighResMIP and only includes compressed data for transfer to JASMIN and the CEDA archives. Data such as check point files and un processed output is not included in the above

Issues Identified

Late completion of runs

The completion dates for each simulation produced by this data flow model are a crude estimation what we would expect to happen. These estimates are strongly dependent on model throughput rates and start dates and small changes to either could easily move the estimated completion date by a month or two. As such all dates should be considered to have an uncertainty of one to two months. The source information for this section is the "Summary data" worksheet from the spreadsheet model. Based on the information supplied as part of [MS22](#) the following issues have been identified:

Met Office

- The High resolution Future AMIP run is expected to be 2 months late, with all other High resolution simulations due to complete just under one month late.

CNR and KNMI

- Future AMIP runs at both resolutions are expected to start and complete shortly after the 1-JAN-2017 deadline. This is probably an error as the Historical AMIP runs these continue from complete in June 2016.

CERFACS

- The performance of CNRM-CM6 is good with all simulations completing with a suitable margin before the deadline, but the completion dates, which require data to be

transferred to JASMIN, are currently missed by 6 months for both the High resolution Coupled simulations. This is due to data transfer rate used (0.2 TB/day) being significantly smaller than the data creation rate (1.0 TB/day) leading to a backlog of data on the source HPC. Improving the data transfer rates above 0.6 TB/day *for each model independently* will allow the D6.4 deadline to be met.

- Experience with data transfer methods such as gridftp and bbftp suggests that transfer rates in the range 2-4 TB/day should be possible with the right tools, so the problems identified here should be straightforward to address.

CMCC

- The current plan for CMCC-CM2 runs involves the simulations being run in series (Historical AMIP, Future AMIP, Coupled Control, Coupled Transient) with each resolution running independently. For the Low resolution simulations the level of performance is sufficient for all deadlines to be met, but the estimated throughput of the high resolution model CMCC-CM2-VHR of 0.5 and the queuing ratio of 1.5 leads to delays of 1 and 2 years for the coupled simulations.
- If the Coupled simulations can be performed in parallel with the Historical and Future AMIP simulations then all deadlines should be met with current performance statistics with a margin of at least 2 months.
- If the sequential nature of running the High resolution simulations is an absolute requirement, then the model throughput would need to be more than doubled to meet the D6.4 deadline.

Data transfer testing

Most groups have used the default value I specified for data transfer rates (5 TB/day). Early suggestions from several groups transferring data for WP2 (e.g. MS4, MS5) is that simple data transfer methods (scp and rsync) struggle to move more than a few hundred GB per day. My prior experience suggests that data transfer rates of 5 TB per day are possible, but that more advanced tools are needed. Data transfer rates in excess of 6 TB per day were routinely achieved between HLRS in Germany and JASMIN using gridftp (part of the globus toolkit) in 2012 and bbcp has been used in similar situations.

JASMIN support teams at STFC do not believe that the volume of data arriving at JASMIN will be a problem for the network; data from the LHC and the Sentinel satellite missions are flowing through the same network infrastructure and the data volumes involved there significantly exceed our requirements.

However, in order to gain confidence that we will not see data transfer bottle necks, we must test the data transfer routes in advance using suitable tools.

Time Series Plots

Core Hour use

The number of core hours needed at each HPC site

Cores in use

The average number of cores in use at each HPC site

Monthly data transfer totals

Monthly data transfer rate

Volumes of data to be transferred to JASMIN each month, along with the amount of data arriving at JASMIN (black line, secondary y-axis).

Average data rate needed to support runs at each institution along with the rate of data arriving at JASMIN (black line, secondary y-axis)

Transferred data totals

Total amount of data transferred from each HPC along with the total amount transferred to JASMIN (black line, secondary y-axis).

Excel spreadsheet model

The spreadsheet used for this analysis is attached to this page: [attachment:MS22_HPC_plan_stream_1_v1.0.xlsm](#). This spreadsheet contains a number of VBA macros to manage the use of the data flow model (as attached to [WP9/Milestone22](#)) for each of the 68 simulations specified as part of Stream 1. This spreadsheet has been developed in Microsoft Excel 2007 and 2010 and may not work well in other versions. It is not my intention for other people to use and update this document (it is not documented well). Should anyone be very keen on investigating it, and you are not disuaded by its complexity here are some notes on its use

1. Input data goes in the HPC_plan_table in the **Run data** sheet. If additional rows are needed then the NUM_ROWS constant in the **populate_and_automate** VBA module needs to be updated. An error should be raised if additional rows are added without changing this constant.
2. The **working** sheet does most of the hard work. The Index value in cell **C2** controls the lookup of all the values in this sheet. Changing this to another suitable integer should change much of this sheet, if you get **#N/A** everywhere then you've put in too large a value.
3. The **Summary data** sheet uses the **working** sheet to calculate a number of quantities. While some of these could be calculated simply from parameters in **Run data** the end dates and data high tide marks cannot. The **Update** button loops over all the runs, updates the **working** sheet and then copies data into this worksheet.
4. The formulae in columns K:M in **Summary data** estimate how early or late the completion of a run is, relative to the corresponding deadline.
5. The **Summary data pivot** uses a pivot table to aggregate the core hours, high tide marks and total data produced on each HPC. **IMPORTANT NOTE:** If you are not familiar with pivot tables in excel, they are a useful tool for aggregating and summarising data. They will not

change until you force them to update. To update a pivot table, select a cell within it and go to the **Options** ribbon under **PivotTable Tools**. The button labelled **Refresh** will update the table or selecting **Refresh All** from the drop down menu below it will update **every** pivot table in the spreadsheet. In German **Refresh** translates as "aktualisieren", please feel free to update this page with the translation in your language if different.

6. There are three data processing worksheets **CPUh data**, **Transfer data**, **Transferred data**. Each worksheet has a button for a macro that loops through each of the simulation runs, updates the **working** work sheet and then copies some of the data. This data is then aggregated across simulations on each HPC platform in columns D:K (column L is used as a total in the transfer sheets).
7. For each data processing worksheet there is at least one Pivot table sheet, aggregating data into monthly means or totals as appropriate. As noted above you need to refresh a pivot table to update its contents. The **CPUh Pivot** worksheet contains some additional formulae to estimate the average number of cores in use in each month.
8. The Pivot Charts in each of the Chart worksheets refer to the pivot tables and should update when their pivot table is refreshed.